

EFFECTIVENESS OF PLACEMENT STRATEGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Statement of the Problem- Low placements is a concern for most of the existing MBA institutes and low performance in this parameter has resulted in the closure of many institutes. Number of placements is also a measure of effectiveness of the placement strategy of the institute.

Objectives –

1. To find out whether all organizations require MBA students for suitable job profiles.
2. To find out whether the demand of experienced MBA pass outs and freshers is same in the chosen organizations
3. To find out whether in selection of MBA students Work Experience is independent of Organization sector .
4. To find out whether within a sector where MBA freshers are required all employers require MBA students or not .

Methodology –

More than 100 employers were contacted using phone to find out whether they require MBA students in their organization and their verbal reply was recorded using Microsoft excel. The data recorded included MBA specializations they prefer and whether they need experienced MBA pass outs or freshers .The research design and type falls in descriptive category. The sampling is Non-Random Quota type of sampling and Z test, Chi Square is applied for testing the formulated hypothesis.

Findings-

The results reveal that not all organizations require MBA freshers. The analysis also reveals that within a sector all employers do not require MBA students and while selecting MBA students work experience does not depend on sector of employment.

Limitations – Data availability on categorization of organization as Micro, Small, Medium and Large organization is a constraint for organizations because of their dynamic asset value and new rubrics introduced by Ministry of Small, Micro and Medium Enterprises which includes turnover .

Keywords : Placement Strategy , Effectiveness , MSME , Job profile , Dynamic asset value

I. Introduction

Fulfilling stakeholders expectations is what every organization is looking at .In professional courses like MBA students enroll with an expectation of becoming employable to get a job with a salary that fulfills their daily needs and results in some savings also .With the number of institutions rising stupendously the competition among institutes is rising to attract students for admission and also to attract as many employers as possible so that their students are placed .Good placements is a result that institutions want to market so that they can portray themselves as a healthy organization which has the inputs to achieve expected results as stated in Figure 1

Figure 1 Stakeholders expectation related to placements

There is no standard action that can help an organization achieve an ideal result with respect to placements .An ideal result will be to achieve 100% placements with a salary that is sufficient to maintain a good standard of living .There are many challenges that an organization has to face to reach this ideal outcome .

Figure 2 Stage wise variation in MBA Education due to various teaching components

The challenges are due to variation in quality of students, the curriculum, the learning style of students, the teaching methodologies used by different teachers and employer requirements as shown in Figure 2 above and many more .To add to the variations some students are not aiming at placements but they are aiming at getting admission in a Higher Degree Program .With so many variations it is very difficult to achieve a standard result hence planning is required .There are different tests used for different skill requirements and according to (Dessler & Varkkey) (K, 2017) (T.Morgan, A.King, R.Weisz, & Schopler, 2004)all tests should be repeatable , standardized , valid and objective in order to be a good test .

Literature Review

Literature was reviewed and the content related to the topics shown in Figure 3 was reviewed.

Figure 3 Main topics on which Literature was reviewed (NAAC) (NBA) (Team A. , Home-ATAL, 2019) (Jawahar Sircar, 2016)

Graduate Outcomes or student expectations based on various accreditation standards and ranking frameworks

Figure 4 Student Expectations as highlighted in ranking frameworks and accreditation standards (NAAC) (NBA) (Team N. , Ranking Metrics for Management)

Figure 5 Sources of Placement Statistics

The Figure 4 highlights student expectations and Figure 5 lists sources of placement statistics. The parameters related to placements in various ranking frameworks/accreditation standards are listed in the

TABLE I below .These also act as a source of placement statistics.

TABLE I DIFFERENT SOURCES FOR PLACEMENT STATISTICS (Team A. , Statistics) (Team N. , NAAC/Home/Info for Institutions/AQAR) (Team N. , NIRF/2020/Ranking/List of participating institutions) (NBA)

S.No	Source	Metric	Metric Number	Description (formula)	Number or % of institutions covered
1	Guidelines for creation of Internal Quality Assurance cell and submission of Annual Quality Assurance Report by accredited institutions by National Assessment and Accreditation Council	Total number of placement of outgoing students during the year	5.2.2	Number of students placed out of the outgoing students during the year	Number of colleges covered =12802 , Number of universities covered =609
2	National Institutional Ranking Framework	Graduation Outcomes (GO) which is a combined metric for previous 3 year results out of 100 marks including 1.Students enrolled in Higher studies and students placed in companies (40 marks) 2.University examination results (20 marks) 3.Median salary (40 marks)	3	1) $40 * ((\% \text{ of graduating students placed in last 3 years} / 100) + (\% \text{ of graduating students selected for higher studies in last 3 years} / 100))$ 2) $20 * (\% \text{ of students passing out the university exams in the last 3 years in the minimum stipulated timeframe out of approved intake} / 100)$ 3) $40 * \text{Median salary of postgraduates}$	630 Management institutes participated in the ranking process in 2020

				passing out from an institution in last 3 years .	
3	National Board of Accreditation	Z=(No. of students placed in companies or Government Sector + No. of students pursuing Ph.D. / Higher Studies + No. of students turned entrepreneur (In the areas related to management discipline)) N=Number of students admitted in first year	B3.3	Placement ,Higher Studies and Entrepreneurship (Z) to Number of students admitted(N) ratio	401 institutions are accredited for MBA or PG Diploma in Management
4	AICTE Website	Number of students placed	Not Applicable	Number of placed students & number of enrolled students	57% approximately (however 12% error in data entered was observed as at for 10 institutes number of placements were greater than number of enrolments)
5	College Brochure & Newspaper Advertisement	Placement percentage	Not Applicable	Placement percentage	Majority of institutions have college brochures.

The Micro-Small-Medium Industry Criteria by MSME

With effect from first July 2020 the rubrics for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises for Service sector and Manufacturing sector industries are clubbed and are now based on **Investment in Plant & Machinery or Equipment** and **Turnover**. The value of Plant & Machinery is dynamic and changes with depreciation and turnover is also dynamic as it is based on market performance. As both the values are dynamic it is very difficult to categorize

an organization is a specific category . According to (Jawahar Sircar, 2016) the investment in plant and machinery does not include installation costs, research and development & pollution control, fire fighting equipment costs, cost of cables, gas producer plants, consultancy cost for erection of plants, storage tanks cost ,cost of power generation sets and extra transformer installed by the enterprise as per the regulations of state electricity board and these are very important categories .Hence segregation as Micro , Small , Medium enterprises will not disclose a comparative analysis on actual present value .

The Data Analysis Based on National Institutional Ranking Framework

It was assumed that the top ranked institutes in National Institutional Ranking Framework are having highest placement % and highest median salaries in India and these institutes are the best placement planners.

Figure 6 Histogram of GPH scores of top 75 NIRF ranked Management Institutions (Team N. , NIRF/2020/Ranking/List of participating institutions)

On doing the analysis of % of placements and % of students going for Higher Education using **Figure 6** it was observed that among the top 75 NIRF ranked institutions 46.7% of institutes scored between 35 to less than 40 out of 40 .The mean score was 32.9 and the sample standard deviation was 6.80 & the median was 34.70 . 32.9 is the average score which is 82.25 % out of 40 so it is assumed that 82.25 % of Indian MBA students are employed in top 75 NIRF ranked institutions.

The Figure 7 histogram for Graduate University Examination Results shows that 85.3 % of the 75 institutions scored between 15 to 20 out of 20 marks .

Figure 7 Histogram for GUE scores of top 75 NIRF Ranked Management Institutes (Team N. , NIRF/2020/Ranking/List of participating institutions)

Figure 8 Probable reasons for 82% employment

Figure 8 states the probable reasons for 82% employment which are either in control or out of control of the institute. Also 64(85.3*0.75) to less than 85.3(85.3*1) % of students pass the MBA exams in first attempt and to pass exams is a certain eligibility criteria. So taking the average only 74.6 % of MBA students pass exams in the first attempt. Employability is possible only after eligibility condition is fulfilled. The collected data is on how many organizations have job profiles for MBA freshers so point 2 is considered to formulate hypothesis.

The Figure 9 histogram for Median Salary results showed that maximum 28 % of institutions scored between 20 to less than 25 out of 40 .

Figure 9 Histogram of MS scores of top 75 ranked Management Institutes (Team N. , NIRF/2020/Ranking/List of participating institutions)

Figure 10 Histogram of 3 years average median salary of top 75 ranked NIRF ranked institutions (Team N. , NIRF/2020/Ranking/List of participating institutions)

TABLE II CORRELATION BETWEEN NIRF RANK AND GPH,GUE,MS SCORES AND MEDIAN SALARY AVERAGE OF 3 YEARS OF AN INSTITUTE

Correlation between various parameters related to Graduate Outcomes & NIRF Rank				
	GPH SCORE	GUE SCORE	MS SCORE	MS AVERAGE
NIRF Rank	- 0.30685	- 0.09027	-0.7757	-0.81231

The **Figure 10** showed that maximum 13.2 % institutions have average median salary between 4 to less than 5 lakhs and 6 to less than 7 lakhs .The TABLE II shows negative correlation between NIRF Rank and graduate outcome parameters .

OBJECTIVES

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2. To find out whether the demand of experienced MBA pass outs and fresher’s is same in the chosen organizations .
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4. To find out whether within a sector where MBA freshers are required all employers require MBA students or not .

Research Methodology

The Figure 11 describes the research methodology and Figure 12 shows that non random sampling of convenience type is used .All employers didnt have an equal chance of selection as employers were selected only from one chosen website randomly at the convenience of the researcher .

Figure 11 Research Methodology

Figure 12 Type of Sampling Used

Hypothesis Testing

The TABLE III below shows all the formulated hypothesis .

TABLE III HYPOTHESIS & TESTS USED (Black, 2011)

S.No.	Hypothesis	Description	Test Used
1.1	H01	It is believed that MBA students are required by 82.25% of all organizations .	Z Test for proportion
1.2	Ha1	It is believed that MBA students are required in less than 82.25% of all organizations .	
2.1	H02	It is believed that the demand of MBA freshers is same as experienced MBA passouts in the chosen organizations .	
2.2	Ha2	It is believed that the demand of MBA freshers is not same as experienced MBA passouts in the chosen organizations .	
3.1	H03	It is believed that Experience wise MBA student requirement is independent of the sector employing .	Chi Square Contingency test
3.2	Ha3	It is believed that Experience wise MBA student requirement is dependent on the sector employing .	
4.1	H04	It is believed that in all sectors where MBA students are required all employers have the same job prospects for MBA freshers.	Chi Square Contingency test
4.2	Ha4	It is believed that in all sectors where MBA students are required all employers do not have the same job prospects for MBA freshers .	

Data Analysis And Findings

1.The number of enterprises district wise are shown in Figure 13 and sector wise distribution is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 13 District wise distribution of chosen enterprises **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 14 Distribution of selected enterprises **Error! Reference source not found.**

3. The status of websites of different enterprises as per (Media) is shown in **Figure 15** .

Figure 15 Status of websites of chosen enterprises

4.The **Figure 16** and **Figure 17** reveal number of employers which require MBA students and the number of employers which immediately need MBA students .Some organizations require MBA students but they need experienced post graduates .Recently IIM Indore revealed that the newly admitted batch consists of 83 % fresh graduates .The general premise is that experienced MBA students have a holistic view of how an organization works ,the interdependencies of different departments .

Figure 16 Distribution of Organizations as MBA Employers and Non-Employers

Figure 17 Distribution of organizations in terms of their immediate requirement of MBA students

5. Hypothesis Testing Results

TABLE IV HYPOTHESIS 1 TESTING

S.No.	Hypothesis	Description	Test Used	Result
1.1	H01	It is believed that MBA students are required by 82.25% of all organizations.	Z Test for proportion	$Z = p1 - 0.8225 / \sqrt{p * q / n}$ p1 = proportion of employers requiring MBA students = 0.196 z calculated = -21.544 z tabulated at 0.05 level of significance = 1.645 As -21.54 is less than -1.645 so it is a failure in accepting null hypothesis .
1.2	Ha1	It is believed that MBA students are required in less than 82.25% of all organizations.		
2.1	H02	It is believed that the demand of MBA freshers is same as experienced MBA passouts in the chosen organizations .	Z Test for proportion	$p1 = 20 / 102 = 0.196078$ $p2 = 3 / 102 = 0.029411$ As population proportions are not known the pooled value to replace the population proportions is 0.001961. Hence $z = -3.763$ At 0.05 level of significance $z = 1.96$ As z tabulated is less than z calculated it is a case of failure to accept null hypothesis .
2.2		It is believed that the demand of MBA freshers is not same as experienced MBA passouts in the chosen organizations .		

Hence from TABLE IV it is concluded that MBA student requirement is in less than 82.25% organizations. **Also the demand of MBA freshers in jobs is not the same as the MBA experienced students and is more than the latter .**

TABLE V CONTINGENCY TABLE FOR HYPOTHESIS 3 TESTING

Sector	O1- Observed Number of Organiz ations requirin g MBA freshers	O2- Observed Number of Organiz ations requirin g Experi encedM BA's	Total	E1- ExpectedN umber of Organizati ons requiring MBA freshers	E2- Expected Number of Organizati ons requiring Experienc ed MBA's	(O1- E1) ² /E 1	(O2- E2) ² /E2
Lead & Lead Products	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130
Building Materials & Construction Equipment Suppliers- Trading of Building Material	8	0	8	6.957	1.043	0.157	1.043
Industrial machineries, machinery parts, machinery tools & supplies	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130
Architects- planner, civil engineer, designer, builders	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130
Pharmaceuticals/ I.V Fluids & Eyes & Ear Drops	1	1	2	1.739	0.261	0.314	2.094
Agriculture implements & equipments	1	1	2	1.739	0.261	0.314	2.094
Kota Stones	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130

Kitchen(modular) ,home-domestic appliances	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130
Office Automation	3	0	3	2.609	0.391	0.059	0.391
Canon Service ,LG Laptop, Desktop	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130
Chemicals	1	0	1	0.870	0.130	0.020	0.130
Event Mgmt	0	1	1	0.870	0.130	0.870	5.797
	20	3	23			1.850	12.33

From

TABLE V Chi Square (Calculated) = 1.85+12.33 =14.18

Chi Square (Tabulated) at 0.05 level of significance and 11 degree of freedom =19.6752

So as Chi Square (Calculated) is less than Chi Square (Tabulated) so it is a case of failure to reject null hypothesis and null hypothesis is accepted, that is **MBA student requirement in different sectors is independent of the Work Experience of the students.**

TABLE VI CONTINGENCY TABLE FOR HYPOTHESIS 4

Sector	O=Observed Number of Employers where MBA freshers are required	E=Expected Number of Employers where MBA freshers are required	(O-E) ² /E
Lead & Lead Products	1	1	0
Building Materials & Construction Equipment Suppliers-Trading of Building Material	8	26	12.46154
Industrial machineries, machinery parts, machinery	1	1	0

tools & supplies			
Architects-planner, civil engineer,designer,builders	1	7	5.142857
I.V Fluids & Eyes & Ear Drops	1	2	0.5
Agriculture implements & equipments	1	21	19.04762
Kota Stones	1	3	1.333333
Kitchen(modular) ,home-domestic appliances	1	3	1.333333
Office Automation	3	9	4
Canon Service ,LG Laptop, Desktop	1	1	0
Chemicals	1	1	0
		Chi Square Calculated	43.81868

As Chi Square (Tabulated) is 23.2090 and (Calculated) is 43.818 from TABLE VI at 0.01 level of significance and 10 degrees of freedom so it is a case of failure to accept null hypothesis which means **that** all employers within a sector do not require MBA students as observed requirements are not equal to expected requirements.

4. Some reasons which emerged for non requirement of MBA students were -

1. Steel knowledge alongwith marketing is essential 2.Current shortage of projects

3.IT, Marketing, Infrastructure Mgmt specific requirements were there and other specialization requirements were not there.

Conclusion

1.The reasons explaining why Placement Planning is important are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18 Reasons for Placement Planning Importance

2.MBA freshers requirement in jobs is far greater than experienced MBA professionals .

3.There is a need to switch to push strategy rather than waiting for employers to visit campus after hearing about the accolades of college which is similar to the pull strategy according to Toyota & Bosch Production Systems . In education system the student skill enhancement is the service employers are looking for .

4.According to (Team N. , NIRF/2020/Ranking/List of participating institutions)NIRF Rank and Graduate Outcome Components have a negative correlation and rank is lowest for institutes having highest Median Salary Scores and highest average Median Salary in last 3 years. GPH is having a negative correlation and GUE is having a very low negative correlation which means higher placements is a stronger indicator of better rank of institutions than university results .

4. Effectiveness can be measured in many ways which are shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19 Ways of measuring effectiveness (Cowan, 1985) (ISO QUALITY MANAGEMENT PRINCIPLES, 2015) (Team E. , 2009)

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

1. It will be interesting to find out the specialization wise requirements in all sectors .
2. It will be interesting to find out whether top 75 ranked NIRF institutions have a placement strategy in place and whether they plan placements in advance .
3. It will be interesting to explore push and pull placement strategies with respect to successful organizations .

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